

The *platinichloride* separated out as pale yellow prisms, m.p. 198° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 13·29. (C₂₃H₂₆O₈NBr, HCl) PtCl₄ requires Pt, 13·38 per cent].

The *methyl ester* was prepared by saturating a suspension of bromonarceine (1 g.) in cold methanol (10 c.c.) with dry HCl, standing for 12 hours and then diluting it with water and making alkaline with sodium carbonate. The precipitate crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 114°. (Found: C, 53·37; H, 5·61. C₂₄H₂₈O₈NBr requires C, 53·53; H, 5·2 per cent).

PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
MADRAS.

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Synthesis of Coumarins from Phenols and β -Ketonic Esters. Part III. Use of Various Condensing Agents.

By DUHKHAHARAN CHAKRAVARTI.

In the condensation of various mono-, di- and trihydric phenols with β -ketonic esters it has been observed that coumarins are produced using sulphuric acid as the condensing agent but phosphorus pentoxide may produce either coumarins or chromones (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129, 407, 619; 1932, 9, 25, 31, 389; cf. Robertson and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1256, 1877, 2426; 1932, 1180, 1681). Excepting in the case of condensation of β -naphthol with unsubstituted acetoacetic ester (Dey and Lakshminarayanan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 153) no other case has been detected where a chromone is formed even in traces using sulphuric acid. Attention was, therefore, directed towards the investigation of the part played by phosphorus pentoxide in the formation of chromones as well as towards the possibility of substituting any other condensing agent for phosphorus pentoxide for the synthesis of chromones. Thus various acidic, basic and neutral condensing agents like phosphoric acid, zinc chloride, hydrochloric acid gas, sodium ethoxide, boric anhydride and sodium acetate have been tried. Zinc chloride and hydrochloric acid gas were previously used by investigators in Pechmann's reaction for the synthesis of coumarins. It is remarkable to note that if condensation takes

place then coumarins are always formed (as shown in the table in the experimental part) and all attempts to find a substitute for phosphorus pentoxide have failed. This singular behaviour of phosphorus pentoxide is noteworthy.

It may also be noted that sulphuric acid in Pechmann's reaction may with advantage be replaced by phosphoric acid particularly in the case of polyhydric phenols (*e.g.*, resorcinol, orcinol, pyrogallol and phloroglucinol), when better yields and purer products are obtained. It has also been found by the author that in Bülow's reaction, which is similar to Pechmann's reaction, the condensation of phenols with β -diketones may also be effected with advantage using sulphuric acid or better phosphoric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -Methylumbelliferone (7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin). (a) *With phosphoric acid.*—Phosphoric acid (*d* 1.75, 30 c.c.) was added to a mixture of resorcin (10 g.) and acetoacetic ester (8 c.c.) and the solution left overnight, when crystals separated. The mixture was poured into water and the solid crystallised as needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 185-86°, yield 80%.

(b) *With sodium acetate.*—A mixture of resorcin (7 g.) and acetoacetic ester (5 g.) was heated for about 10 hours at 190°-200° with fused sodium acetate (20 g.). The mass was then washed with water and crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 185°, yield 72%.

(c) *With boric anhydride.*—Resorcin (7 g.), acetoacetic ester (5 g.) and boric anhydride (20 g.) were heated on the water-bath for about 10 hours. The mixture was then treated with dilute sodium carbonate solution and the residue crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 185°, yield 50%.

(d) *With sodium ethoxide.*—Resorcin (5 g.) was added to a solution of acetoacetic ester (5 g.) in an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide (1 g. of sodium in 25 c. c. of alcohol) and the solution heated for 15 minutes on the water-bath, when the sodium salt separated. The solution was diluted with water, acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 185°, yield 54%.

The melting point of the products in all these cases was not depressed when mixed with β -methylumbelliferone. The acetyl

derivatives, prepared by heating the substances with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, crystallised in needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 150°, identical with the acetyl derivative of β -methylumbelliferone of Pechmann.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic ester was prepared by the condensation of resorcin (10 g.) and ethyl acetosuccinate (10 g.) in presence of phosphorus pentoxide (40 g.). The reaction set in with much evolution of heat on warming on the water-bath. After 15 minutes the product was treated with ice-cold water and the precipitate washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 163°, the m. p. being not depressed when mixed with a specimen prepared in presence of sulphuric acid (Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 777). The identical compound was also obtained by condensing resorcin (3 g.) with ethyl acetosuccinate (4 g.) using phosphoric acid (15 c.c.)

5-Hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin-3-acetic ester.—It was prepared by adding concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) to a mixture of orcinol (4 g.) and ethyl acetosuccinate (5 g.) in the cold. It was isolated as usual and crystallised from rectified spirit in colourless plates, m.p. 198-200°. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 5.4. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8 per cent).

The identical compound was also obtained by the condensation of orcinol (10 g.) with ethyl acetosuccinate (10 g.) in presence of phosphorus pentoxide (30 g.). The reaction was complete on heating on the water-bath for 15 minutes, when the product was treated with ice-cold water and the precipitate washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 198-200°, the m. p. being not depressed when mixed with a specimen of the compound prepared above using sulphuric acid. The same compound was also obtained by condensing orcinol (5 g.) with ethyl acetosuccinate (4 g.) using phosphoric acid (20 c. c.).

7:8-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic ester was prepared by the condensation of pyrogallol with ethyl acetosuccinate in presence of sulphuric acid in the usual manner. It was isolated as usual and crystallised from rectified spirit in colourless needles, m. p. 186°. (Found: C, 60.2; H, 4.9. $C_{14}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 60.43; H, 5.04 per cent).

The compounds, prepared with different condensing agents, are tabulated below.

Reactants.	Condensing agent.	Product.	M. p.
Orcin + acetoacetic ester	H ₃ PO ₄	5-Hydroxy-4 :7-dimethyl-coumarin	250°
Pyrogallol + acetoacetic ester	H ₃ PO ₄	7 :8-Dihydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin	235°
Phloroglucinol + acetoacetic ester	H ₃ PO ₄	5 :7-Dihydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin	285°
Pyrogallol + phenylacetoacetic ester	H ₃ PO ₄	7 :8-Dihydroxy-3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin	268°
Resorcin + benzoylacetic ester	H ₃ PO ₄	7-Hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin	240°
Pyrogallol + benzoylacetic ester	H ₃ PO ₄	7 :8-Dihydroxy-4 phenylcoumarin	188°
Resorcin + benzylacetoacetic ester	H ₃ PO ₄ or Na acetate or Na ethoxide	7-Hydroxy-3 benzyl-4-methylcoumarin	224°
Resorcin + methylacetoacetic ester	H ₃ PO ₄ or Na acetate. or Na ethoxide.	7-Hydroxy-3 :4-dimethylcoumarin	256°
α -Naphthol + acetoacetic ester	H ₃ PO ₄ or Na acetate.	4-Methyl-1 :2- α -naphthapyrone.	168°
β -Naphthol + acetoacetic ester	Na acetate	4-Methyl-1 :2- β -naphthapyrone and 2-methyl-1 :4- β -naphthapyrone, forming the styrene derivative with benzaldehyde, m. p. 198°.	179°
<i>p</i> -Cresol + acetoacetic ester.	H ₃ PO ₄	4:6-Dimethylcoumarin	150°

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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